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A RESEARCH REVIEW OF GLASS CEILING FOR WOMEN EMPLOYEES IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

A "glass ceiling" refers to that invisible barrier beyond which minorities, in particular women in middle level management, never rise. Silent, yet unreachable, this barrier is one of the root causes why the percentage of women occupying top-level management is much lesser than men. Some women like Indra Nooyi, Chanda Kocchar, Nishi Vasudeva, Shikha Sharma, Simone Tata and Kiran Mazumdar- Shaw. Etc. has managed to break the glass but the numbers are too few. Gender- based discriminations form a major hurdle in the path of promotions or salary hikes at senior levels creating a euphemism for bias against women talent at work. Not only are the high positions considered as male dominated, there are lot of other factors such as (socio-cultural, legal, personal) that prevents the female force from climbing the top ladder. According to the latest Grant Thornton's International Business Report, 40% of businesses worldwide have no women in senior management, a figure that has remained unchanged since 2004. However, the good news is that Asian countries have an edge over the rest of the world.

The present paper attempts to review the previous literature on this topic with giving its own findings and suggestions.

Keywords: Glass Ceiling, Gender discrimination, Gender gap, Management, Organization.

INTRODUCTION:

The term "**Glass Ceiling**" was coined in a 1986 Wall Street Journal Report on Corporate Women by Hymowitz and Schellhardt. The invisible barrier affects working women the most as it diminishes any chances of advancement for someone who is career conscious such discrimination leads women to have feelings of low self-esteem, decreased motivation and slowing down of interest in their jobs. One of the many fangs of the glass ceiling effect is the evident difference in wages for the same job. Also, concern is given inferior statuses within the counter partners.

The definition "**The Glass Ceiling**" refers to an invisible barrier that limits the level to which a woman or another member of a demographic minority can advance within the hierarchy in an organization.

In 1991 The Glass Ceiling Commission was established and the U.S. Department of Labor defined "those artificial barriers based on attitudinal or organizational bias that prevent qualified individuals from advancing upward in their organization into management-level positions" as Glass Ceiling. The limitation is normally based upon some form of discrimination, most often being sexism. During 1991 to 1996 the department's Glass Ceiling Commission studied how these barriers, not only as they apply to women, but to minorities as well.

According to Wikipedia in Economics, the term **glass ceiling** refers to the scene, yet unbreakable barrier that keeps minorities and women from rising to the upper rungs of the corporate ladder, regardless of their qualifications or achievements".

Initially, the metaphor applied to barriers in the careers of women but was quickly extended to refer to obstacles hindering the advancement of minority men, as well as women.

David Cotter et al. defined four distinctive characteristics that must be met to conclude that a *glass ceiling* exists. A glass ceiling inequality represents:

1. "A gender or racial difference that is not explained by other job-relevant characteristics of the employee."
2. "A gender or racial difference that is greater at higher levels of an outcome than at lower levels of an outcome."
3. "A gender or racial inequality in the chances of advancement into higher levels, not merely the proportions of each gender or race currently at those higher levels."
4. "A gender or racial inequality that increases over the course of a career."

Cotter and his colleagues found that glass ceilings are a distinctively gender phenomenon. Both white and African-American women face a glass ceiling in the course of their careers. In contrast, the researchers did not find evidence of a glass ceiling for African-American men.

There are many different impediments placed upon women that make it difficult for them to attain a higher work status. With these very negative effects on women and their self-esteem, the glass ceiling has created an even larger problem than just in the work place. Most see the glass ceiling as only being in the work place, which is where it originally was intended for, it has spread to encompass the household and others as well. The barrier within the household has been seen as the difficulty a woman has of getting out of the household and accumulating a job. Not all women feel as though they are being suppressed in the household and many women choose to be in the household in which case the glass ceiling does not apply to them. The term only applies to those women that wish to be out in the work field but are unable to be. Because the glass ceiling also limits the opportunities of women in developing countries, the term has broadened and also become an issue around the world.

GLASS CEILING IN INDIA:

In India the Glass ceiling exists at some levels though in the recent time cracks in the glass ceiling is being observed as Indian women are pushing forward in their own respective fields to break this classical approach and earn both name and fame. We will study the statistical data of women economic participation to understand how much the females are contributing according to the government figures.

1) Women in the Labour Force

- In 2009-2010, women were 20 to 6.1% of all rural workers, and 13.8% of all urban workers.

- Women are an estimated 30% of all economically active individuals. The participation rate for women is falling: from 37% in 2004-05 to 29% in 2009-10.
- Women earn 62% of men's salary for equal work.

2) Labour Force Trends and Legislation

- For women's economic participation, India ranked 124th, (towards the bottom of the 136 countries listed in the 2013 *Global Gender Gap Index*), and for women's educational opportunity a ranking of 120.
- India has a young workforce and population. In the next ten years, with both younger people and women entering the workforce, India expects to add an additional 110 million people to its labour force.
- In 2013, India passed the *Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace (Prevention, Prohibition and Redressal) Act* to provide protection against sexual harassment in the workplace.

3) Management

- Women are just 3% of legislative, management, and senior official positions.
- In 2010, Women held only 5.3% of board directorships of BSE-100 companies.
- 22.6% of women are employed in business and they make up 14% of senior management roles.
- According to Gender Diversity Benchmark, 2011, India has the lowest national female labour force and the worst leaking pipeline for junior to middle level position women.
 - 28.71% of those at the junior level of the workplace
 - 14.9% of those at the middle level
 - 9.32% of those at the senior level.

- Out of 323 total executive directorship positions (generally considered to be prerequisites to holding the CEO position) on the Bombay Stock Exchange 100, just eight (2.5%) are held by women.
 - 54% of companies on the Bombay Stock Exchange 100 have no women board directors.
- Despite occupying small percentages of leadership positions, 97.2% of women (compared to 95.6% of men) aspire to jobs with increased responsibility.

4) Women in Government

- In June 2014, India was ranked 116 out of 189 countries ranked in descending order for percentage of women in Parliaments.

(Source: Catalyst. *Quick Take: Women in the Labour Force in India*. New York: Catalyst, 2014)

BREAKING THE GLASS CEILING IN INDIA

Women leaders confront gender inequality in India (UNDP INDIA) 14 Mar 2012

India has a rich history of women in positions of power, yet the country ranks 129 out of 146 countries on the Gender Inequality Index, and women in India face barriers at all levels in areas such as food insecurity and education. To confront the social, economic and political challenges faced by women in India, a group of female activists, local leaders and entrepreneurs in New Delhi met with Helen Clark, chief of the United Nations Development Programme on Wednesday. "Over the years women in government at the local level have gained a new sense of power," Clark said. "These gains have to be protected and used effectively to make a meaningful difference in the lives of all women, and provide space for leadership among women to emerge at different levels."

Cracks in the Glass Ceiling- The next five years are going to be an interesting place for senior women leaders in the corporate world in India. We are going to see an increasing number make it to the top,

and more important, stay there, says **Priya Chetty-Rajagopal, Vice President & Client Partner, Stanton Chase International.**

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

1. To study the existing literature (Research paper) on Glass Ceiling in India.
2. To identify the social, personal and organizational factors for the gender discrimination that exists in the private and public corporate sector.
3. To understand the problem deeply and the impact it is creating on the female employees attitude towards their corporate roles and responsibilities.
4. To evaluate the role of organizations regarding the existing Glass Ceiling effect.
5. To propose suggestions on how the organizations and the government can address this problem of Glass Ceiling which can help in increasing the ratio of female workforce in climbing the top ladder.
6. To make some common solution that can apply to discover the solution.

HYPOTHESES OF STUDY:

- 1) Glass Ceiling has a wide scope in the present scenario.
- 2) Glass ceiling affects the career progression of women in today's competitive world.
- 3) It affects the growth of society on whole.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

A. Data Collection :

The data is collected from two sources i.e. Primary and secondary sources. The primary data is collected from experts in public and private corporate industries. The secondary data is collected from the journals and published research paper of various author on Glass Ceiling (Major portion of data collected from already published research paper on given topic/area)

B. Sample Design :

For research work, the sample design will be as under...

1. Sample Size - 10 respondents from private and public organizations.
2. Sampling Technique – Convenience Sampling Method.
3. Universe/Population - Amravati (Maharashtra)

C. Data Analysis:

Analysis of the data will be done on the basis of rational thinking of the author. The interpretation will be based on the analysis from this conclusion will be derived and the recommendation will be given.

D. Tools of Research:

Pre- structured questionnaire, interview of respondents and the observation will takes into consideration during the research.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

The literature review is done with the help of various published paper on Glass Ceiling. The main objective behind the literature review is to consider the critical points of current knowledge including substantive findings, as well as theoretical and methodological contributions to a particular topic.

Author Usha Kiran Rai in her research paper “Women Executives and the glass ceiling: Myths and Mysteries from Razia Sultana to Hillary Clinton” concluded her views as under...

According to her research, in India the status of women has long been contradictory. Across the world, including the most developed nations; women are not to be seen in the top positions in the corporate sector. Despite the fact that 68 women have led their countries as presidents and prime minister, there still exist many barriers in the career path of women leading to leadership positions. Some of the barriers are related to the women themselves, and some to their organizations. They examined these barriers, and consider what can be done to facilitate a faster pace of change, in order to develop and utilize women’s talents more for their mutual benefit. Today, the workforce is changing. Social values and mores, and the increased global focus on women’s issues have changed the woman’s role impacting the career progression of women. Gradually, women managers in India have been successful in rising to top positions in Indian organizations, despite a culture that might suggest otherwise. These women were successful because of the interplay of organizational and family support, coupled with the individual drive for success, each woman demonstrated. They concluded that there is a persistable scope for women to excel in the corporate sector, if they learn to balance several resources like time, ideas, finance and relationships.

Women’s Low Representation in Management jobs

The study by Koshal, et al (2006), states that in India 2 women per 100 economically active men take administrative and managerial positions in India. The Confederation of Indian Industry released a study “Understanding the Levels of Empowerment of Women in the Workplace in India” covering 149 large and medium size companies across regions, which highlights that women comprise 16 percent at junior management level, 4 percent each at middle and senior levels and only 1 percent in organizational leadership positions (CEOs). According to the International Business Owners Survey (IBOS) 2004 by Grant Thornton, 42% (59% globally) of business in India include women in senior management positions, but women occupy 12% (19% globally) of the senior management posts available.

The ASSOCHAM study reveals that educated metros and large town females are opting for self employment. Women are very well informed still denied promotions and better career prospects and amply face gender biases. It asserts that there is a need for a National Policy for promoting women in top levels of management. Only 3.3% of women are elevated to key positions while 78.9% continues to slog at humble positions and 17.7% of them despite working very hard are able to end up their career at middle management cadre.

Sanghamitra Buddhapriya in her study “Women in Management” states that women in the senior management positions are highly underrepresented. In India, she says although women have entered management since decades yet it is surprising to know that there is no government sponsored systematic data ascertaining the number of women in management in India. She states that in the Public sector units where some data exists it is disheartening to know that women are grossly underrepresented.

Vimolwan Yukongdi and John Benson in the book “Women in Asian Management” have spelled out the factors that inhibit women’s growth. They also attribute women’s slow growth to mainly individual and societal factors. They agree with Kulkarni (2002) who in his study “Women and Professional Competency” states that it is the traditional and cultural inhibitions acquired by women from childhood, nurtured by parents and reinforced by socialization which is the key hurdle that inhibited their urge to be in the executive or leadership position. This is further supplemented by lack of self direction, independence and self motivation.

Ashok Gupta and Koshal (2001) insist that the tussle created by motherhood and career ambition is known to affect women’s career. The inhibiting factors include reluctance to travel, getting transferred

and living away from families remains a significant barrier. Added it is women's exclusion from informal networks which also make them lose out opportunities for promotion.

Pawan S. Budhwar, Debi S. Saini, and Jyotsna Bhatnagar in their work "Women in Management in the New Economic Environment: The Case of India" argue that historically, women in India have not enjoyed a good status in workplace settings whether in managerial or operative roles. The biggest challenge they face today is balancing dual role of organizational managers and housewives and the differential treatment meted out to them at work, which upholds the centrality and superiority of men. Due to stereotypes they are offered less challenging jobs and are often not involved in tackling crucial organizational issues.

CONCLUDING REMARKS:

This study helps in finding the current status of the glass ceiling that exists in our organizations. Through this study we can analyze and find solutions in overcoming the problems faced by the female workforce in reaching the top positions in our country.

We have studied that In India, the status of women has long been contradictory. Across the world, including the most developed nations; women are not to be seen in the top positions in the corporate sector. The review of literature on women in management across the countries and in India shows that there are certain universal features apart from the cultural attributes and specificities for which there is so low representation of women in management jobs. Some of the barriers are related to the women themselves, and some to their organizations. Most of the women managers hold lower and middle management positions and the number of women remains extremely small in top management positions. Factors that restrict women managers to reach the top ladder are blocked opportunity, lack of support of employers, limited access to information, restricted access to training's, marriage and motherhood, conflict between career and family responsibilities, prioritization of family over career, immobility of women and stereotypical attitude towards women managers. In the organizational structures discrimination against women managers exist relating to remuneration, job allocation, performance appraisal, promotion, training opportunities and reward structures. In the Indian context the fact that not much literature and data exists about women managers itself reflects the lack of attention paid to this subject. Few studies that have been done in India explore women representation in management and cursorily draw attention to the factors contributing to their low representation. Some of those challenges are common to what has been discussed above. However there are certain constrains faced by Indian women managers which are unique to Indian situation and are more to do with cultural and social factors which can be traced back to deep rooted images of traditional women role. Gender differences appear more deeply embedded in India than in Western societies which is very much apparent in the workplace.

On the other hand a new picture is emerging in today's corporate world; the scenario is changing with the change in the workforce. With the increased global focus on women's issues have changed the woman's role impacting the career progression of women. Gradually, women managers in India have been successful in rising to top positions in Indian organizations, despite a culture that might suggest otherwise. There are women who have taken on the entire world: Indra Nooyi, CEO, Pepsico; Naina Lal Kidwai, MD, HSBC India; Lalita Gupte; JMD, ICICI; Pragya Raman, Group Executive President of Aditya Birla Group; Chanda Kochhar, CEO, ICICI bank; Renu Karnad, Executive Director, HDFC; Kavita Hurry, MD, ING Vysya Mutual Fund, Shikha Sharma, CEO andMD, Axis Bank, Kalpana Morparia, country head of JPMorgan to name a few. These women were successful because of the interplay of organizational and family support, coupled with the individual drive for success, each woman demonstrated. We conclude that there is a persistable scope for women to excel in the corporate sector, if they learn to balance several resources like time, ideas, finance and relationships and if they are well supported by the organizations.

REFERENCES:

1. Women leaders confront gender inequality in India (UNDP INDIA)
2. Roy chowdhury .I. "Glass-Ceiling: The case of Razia Sultana" HRM REVIEW, 2009
3. <http://www.accenture.com/microsites/vaahini/opinion/Pages/cracks-in-the-glass-ceiling.aspx>
4. Koshal, Manjulika, Koshal, Rajindar K. & Gupta, Ashok (2006). *Women managers in India: challenges and opportunities*. In *Management in India: Trends and Transition*/edited by Herbert J. Davis, Samir R. Chatterjee and Mark Heuer. New Delhi, Response Books, 2006.
5. *Women cry bias at work*. The Telegraph, Calcutta. Saturday, April 15, 2006
6. Grant Thornton (2004). *International Business Owners Survey (IBOS)*. Available at www.grantthornton.ca/surveys/GT_IBOS_2004_.pdf
7. Reddy, Y. "Women executives: Glass ceiling myths and mysteries": HRM REVIEW, 9(8), 2009(August): 41-43.
8. Roychowdhury .I. "Glass-Ceiling: The case of Razia Sultana" HRM REVIEW, 2009
9. (March) 27-29.'Glass ceiling is in evidence' Times of India, Aug 26, 2006, 12.05am
10. IST<http://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/articleshow/1927611.cms>Women CEOs who broke the glass ceiling in India<http://business.rediff.com/slide-show/2009/dec/01/slide-show-1-more-women-ceos-in-india-than-abroad.htm#contentTop>The Corporate Glass Ceiling,

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Some of the portion of this paper is taken from various sites and articles. The broad objective of this paper is to spread the knowledge regarding particular subject, publication is one of the initiative taken for fulfillment of this objective. There is no any monetary intention behind the publication.

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